

SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOMONYMIC WORDS IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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This article examines the semantic characteristics of homonymic words in English and Russian languages. It analyzes the differences between the two languages and their meanings. There is also a comparative analysis of English and Russian words.

A semantic and comparative study of homonyms in English and Russian languages is important to analyze differences between the two languages such as sounds and the meaning of words in both languages. It is necessary for the developing techniques of teaching in both languages. The etymology of homonymy came from the ancient Greek, meaning "homos" the same or equal and "онома" it means "name". The word *homonymy* began to be used in the English language in the 16th century. Homonymy is a linguistic phenomenon. Homonymic words- are the same spelling, pronunciation and sound but different meanings.

The analysis of two languages in the homonymy phenomenon of linguistic. Many researchers have studied the phenomenon of the homonymic words. Reformatskiy wrote in his book that homonymic word is with the same pronunciation, phonetical and morphological structure of the word [1]. For example, in Russian language the word "лук" (Растение) it means "plant" and another meaning "лук (оружие) is weapon. Such homonyms arise in a language through borrowed words or the phonetical structure. There are also some cases where the same roots, independently of another, same words, in the same part of the speech and with the same inflectional coincidences for example, голубец – "голубая краска" and голубец- "блюдо из фарша и капусты". In Russian the largest number of homonyms arose due to borrowings, for example, "балка- "овраг" (Turkic) and балка- "бревно" (German) лама – "монах" (Tibetan) and лама "животное" (Spanish). In English language the bulk of homonyms arose after the Middle English vowel shift, for example, the word "deer" (олень) and dear (дорогой). The problem of homonymy in linguistics began to be studied in the Middle Ages and was studied not only lexically-semantically, but also structurally-grammatically. In the first quarter of the 19th century, the Russian researcher I.F. Kalaidovich in his "Experience of Rules for Creating a Terminological Dictionary of the Russian Language" wrote homonyms that has different meanings but the same structure.

List of homonyms in English language

Abstract	Action	Alarm	Ball	Bank	Arm
Based on general ideas	A legal process	Fear or distress	A round object	The side of a river	limb
summary	Fighting in a war	Alarm clock	A formal party with dance	A financial organization	To provide weapons

List of homonyms in Russian language

Лук	Мышь	Мир	Среда
Овощ(vegetable)	Грызун(mouse)	Земля (Earth)	День недели (Wednesday)
Оружие(weapon)	Компьютерное устройство (computer's device)	Отсутствие войны (peace)	Место обитания (environment)

The comparative analysis of two languages, English and Russian, also includes some words in English and Russian languages. This term is "Interlingual homonyms" that are similar in spelling or pronunciation in different languages, but differ in meaning. This figurative expression is used to denote lexemes. For example, the English word "artist"- a person who creates paintings and in Russian language "артист" it means a person who sings songs.

English words	Russian words
Book- a written or printed work including pages.	Бук (type of tree)
Box- a container with a flat base and sides	Бокс (kind of sport)
Clever- smart person who knows a and learns a lot.	Клевер (plant)
Look- direct one's gaze or see something	Лук (vegetable)

S.Ullmann believes that it is easy to imagine the language without homonymy such a language would be more effective for communication skill than a language with homonyms" and he thinks that " homonymy is a statistical universal high degree of probability"[5]. V.V. Vinogradov highlights that the problem of homonymy is given great significance in a wide variety of linguistic concepts and in a wide variety of linguistic research [3].

The main causes of homonymy: 1) The result of phonetical change, 2) semantic changes and morphological simplification 3) borrowing words from other languages. The most common reason for the emergence of homonym is the coincidence in form of two or more words that originated from different languages, in the process of language development, merged into a similar sound and grammatical form. In the study of homonymy, researchers noticed that there was a strong influence of French on English before the Norman Conquest years. Another reason for the emergence of homonymy is the loss of connection between the meanings of a single polysemantic word. For example, the word "flower" means a type of plant and "flour" means milled wheat. Furthermore, the English language tends to shorten form of words and it is leading to the emergence of new homonymic words. For example, the words "fan" which came from "fanatic" and "fan" it means "wind". Walter Scott divided the form of homonymy into 3 groups:

1. Lexical homonyms- that refer to the same part of speech and same sound and spelling but have different meanings "ball" (a spherical object) and "ball" (a formal party). In Russian language, *КЛЮЧ* (it means "key") and *КЛЮЧ* (source and spring).

2. Grammatical homonyms- that refer to the same sound and spell, but belong to different meaning and grammatical functions. However, they have some common meaning, for example, "brother's (possessive) or brothers (in a plural form)

3. Lexico-grammatical homonyms- they have different grammatical and lexical characteristics. train" noun (the type of transport-vehicle) to "train" verb (to teach) or "rose" noun (a flower) and "rose" verb (past form of rise).

The study of homonymy, in which we analyzed some words, found their meaning and characterized the differences of homonymic words and it is a specific aspect of linguistics, especially since the 1920s. A large number of linguists have studied the phenomenon of homonymy, when did it come and which factors did influence on languages? According to another classification which invented and developed by Smirnitskiy [4], homonyms are divided into:

Absolute homonyms- same sound and spelling "left" (on towards or direction) and "left" past form of leave (to have departed or quit).

Homophones are homonyms that sound the same but words are written differently, "sun" and "son".

Homographs are homonyms that words are spelled the same but sound different, "bow" (a bending of the head or body) and "bow" (a knot tied with two loops and two loose ends).

Paronyms are homonyms that have similar spelling and pronunciation, but they are not identical, "lose" (become unable to find) and "loose" (not firmly or tightly fixed in a place).

Interlingual homonyms are homonyms that are similar in spelling or pronunciation in different language, but differ in meaning. In English the word "magazine" (a periodical publication containing articles, news) and in Russian language it means "shop".

Homonymy is a complex phenomenon in the linguistic field. Linguists have found that the study of homonyms in a foreign language is difficult and also it is a significant part in linguistic. As a result, we analyzed English and Russian words which contained homonymic words and studied the classification of homonymy with examples.

References:

1. Khisamova, V., Abdullina, L., Nurgalieva, L. and Khabibullina, E., 2020. Classification of Homonymic Terms in Medical Terminology of English, Russian and Tatar Languages. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 10(6), pp.18-34.
2. Krovetz, R., 1997, July. Homonymy and polysemy in information retrieval. In *35th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and 8th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics* (pp. 72-79).
3. Pospelov, N.S., 1961. *Viktor Vladimirovich Vinogradov* (No. JPRS4429).
4. Smirnickij, A.I., 1956. *Leksikologiya anglijskogo jazyka* [Lexicology of the English language]. *M.: Izd-vo liter. na inostr. jazykakh*.
5. Ullmann, S., 1953. Descriptive semantics and linguistic typology. *Word*, 9(3), pp.225-240.